

Self-Efficacy Mediated Spiritual Leadership on Citizenship Behavior Towards the Environment of Employees at Harapan Keluarga Hospital

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Abstract:- This research aims to examine the influence of Spiritual Leadership on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment with Self-efficacy as a mediator. This type of research uses quantitative research methods with a causal associative approach. The sample was taken using a simple random sampling technique, namely 136 respondents from a total population of 205 employees at Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital, Lombok. Data analysis uses the SEM-PLS technique using SMART PLS software. The results of this research indicate that Spiritual Leadership has a significant positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment. Self-efficacy can mediate the positive influence of Spiritual Leadership on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment. Therefore, management needs to adopt Spiritual Leadership in an effort to encourage their employees to behave more pro-environmentally on a discretionary basis because in aggregate it can benefit the natural environment and the organization's finances.

Keywords:- *Spiritual Leadership, Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment, Self-Efficacy.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Environmental awareness efforts or actions that support sustainability within organizations are often based on independent individual initiatives (Boiral et al, 2015). Therefore, organizational efforts to encourage their employees to behave pro-environmentally attract the interest of researchers, such as Boiral and Paillé (2012), Daily et al., (2009), Robertson and Barling (2017), because they are considered to have an important contribution to organizational efforts in environmental Conservation. However, as stated by Robertson and Barling (2017), environmentally conscious behavior in the workplace, like many new conceptions, is still conceptualized and measured in different ways and often without underlying organizing theory.

Voluntary employee behavior that benefits the organization is conceptualized by Organ (1988) with the term Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) which is defined as individual behavior that is discretionary, not recognized directly or explicitly by the formal reward system and in aggregate promotes the effective functioning of the

organization. In 2009, Boiral developed the OCB concept which focused more on employee environmental care behavior in contributing to the organization's pro-environmental performance, then by Daily et al. (2009) used the term Organizational Citizenship Behavior toward the Environment (OCBE), namely discretionary individual social behavior, not recognized directly or explicitly by the formal reward system and contributing to increasing effective pro-environment management by the organization.

Research on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment, such as that conducted by Boiral and Paillé (2012), Robertson and Barling (2017), Testa et al (2018) and Jiang et al (2019) shows that the OCBE concept can help organizations in their efforts to be more environmentally conscious and environmentally friendly with their employees as the main actors in these efforts. However, OCBE as a discretionary individual behavior that is independent of the organizational reward system, requires a trigger so that it can grow and develop within the individual and cannot immediately arise due to the demands of the organization's internal operating standards or due to management regulations (Testa et al., 2018).

OCBE as a new behavior needs to be learned by individuals and requires exemplary figures as role models, as explained by Bandura (1977) in social learning theory, which states that most human behavior is learned observationally, namely by observing other people, so by looking how other people behave, new concepts will emerge that are believed to be the right way to act. This is because human behavior has a continuous reciprocal interaction between cognitive, behavioral and environmental influences. The other people referred to by Bandura (1977) could be colleagues or leaders in the work environment, but the person who has the greatest potential to influence other people's behavior is the leader.)

Indeed, both leadership and management are concerned with providing direction for the organization. However, if management is about planning, organizing, staffing, directing and controlling, then leadership is about motivating other people to change (Fry, 2003). Therefore, many previous studies have examined the influence of various types of leadership styles on OCBE, such as research by Gumani et al. (2021), Ullah et al. (2021), Aboramadan et al. (2021), Islam et al. (2021), Abbas et al. (2022) and Liu and Yu (2023) with

varying results depending on the leadership style used and research location.

When humans work, they will not only fulfill their worldly physical needs, but whenever possible, they will try to find a higher meaning as a manifestation of their human side, one of which is the desire to make positive changes for the people around them. This is considered by Fry (2003) to be in line with the aim of spiritual leadership to create alignment of vision and values at all strategic levels, teams and empowered individuals which are ultimately used to encourage higher organizational commitment and productivity.

Spiritual Leadership is a more holistic leadership style that integrates four fundamental arenas that determine the essence of human existence, namely body (physical), mind (logical/rational thinking), heart (emotions, feelings), and soul (Moxley, 2000). Fry (2003) then developed a causal model of Spiritual Leadership, where the values, attitudes, and behavior shown by the leader show employees that the leader has a clear vision which is reflected in an altruistic attitude of love that gives employees hope and confidence to their leader. This morally makes employees find a higher meaning than just working to get rewards and encourages them to make positive changes because employees feel appreciated and understood as humans. This condition in aggregate creates a contribution to the organization in the form of commitment and productivity.

Research that specifically looks at the influence of Spiritual Leadership on OCBE is still limited so far, such as research by Afsar et al. (2015) which shows that Spiritual Leadership has no direct effect on Pro-Environmental Behavior / OCBE and requires mediator variables, such as Workplace Spirituality, Environmental Passion and Intrinsic Motivation. However, research by Anser et al. (2020) shows that Spiritual Leadership directly has a significant positive effect on OCBE, apart from through Environmental Justice Orientation as a mediator. In this research, specifically, Anser et al. (2020) place the function of Spiritual Leadership in two positions, namely being a role model and creating and facilitating the process of collective social influence.

As a role model, Spiritual Leadership is an example of applying the values of altruistic love, such as magnanimity, forgiveness, helping each other, and helping selflessly which then makes a positive contribution to the emotional, moral, and spiritual development of employees and allows them to develop a self-regulation approach and help them make better moral choices. This function makes employees believe that they are capable of carrying out this behavior because they have concrete examples that they can emulate. This belief also shapes employees to prepare themselves for future changes, this is what Bandura (1977) calls part of self-efficacy. Self-efficacy expectations, according to Bandura (1977), are the strongest determinant of behavior change because self-efficacy expectations determine the initial decision to carry out behavior, the effort expended, and persistence in facing difficulties. Research by Chen et al. (2011) also shows that Spiritual Leadership has a positive effect on followers'

spiritual attributes toward inner self (self-esteem and self-efficacy).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. *Spiritual Leadership*

The concept of Spiritual Leadership has emerged since the 1980s through research conducted by Townsend (1984) and Sanders (1986). However, this research focuses more on managing leadership values in the Christian religion, is researched in the context of education and teaching specifically in the Christian religion and has not discussed its potential in the world of work or companies. The conception of Spiritual Leadership as a more holistic leadership style, which is inspired by noble religious values and spiritual teachings but is not tied to a particular religion in its relationship and influence on a general organization was first developed by Fry (2003). In his research, Fry (2003) emphasized that the concept of Spiritual Leadership that he developed was indeed inspired by the noble values of various religious teachings as well as several leadership styles such as ethical leadership and servant leadership but was not exclusively linked to certain religious practices and focused more on values. Universally spiritual by combining vision, hope, altruistic love, workplace spirituality theory, and spiritual purpose. This atmosphere builds coherence between leaders and employees so that they can influence a more positive work environment. The leader or principal who puts forward integrity, honesty, and humility positively affects the perception of teachers in their workplace (Ansory et al., 2022).

B. *Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment*

Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment is a behavioral concept that developed from the concept of Organizational Citizenship Behavior first proposed by Organ (1988) which is defined as individual behavior that is discretionary, not recognized directly or explicitly by the formal reward system, and in aggregate promotes the functioning of the organization effectively. This concept was then developed for the first time to specifically focus on pro-environmental behavior by Boiral (2009) and then by Daily et al (2009) then referred to as Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment, namely individual social behavior that is discretionary, not recognized directly or indirectly. explicit by formal reward systems and contribute to the promotion of effective pro-environmental management by organizations. Robertson and Barling (2017) then refined the definition of Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment as discretionary individual behavior, not recognized directly or explicitly by a formal reward system and in aggregate directly benefits the natural environment and indirectly contributes to the organization and benefits individuals as a whole. Specific.

C. *Self-efficacy*

Bandura (1997) defines self-efficacy as an individual's self-confidence or belief in their ability to do something, produce something, organize, achieve goals and implement actions to realize certain skills. Individuals with self-efficacy believe that they can do something to change the events

around them. Individuals with low self-efficacy consider themselves unable to do everything around them. In difficult situations, individuals with low self-efficacy tend to give up easily (Arial et al., 2022). Sherer et al. (1982) emphasized that Self-efficacy is a specific condition of self-confidence focused on certain things and situations where individuals who often experience success and success in the past tend to have higher Self-efficacy than individuals who often experience failure in the past. Then.

D. The Influence of Spiritual Leadership on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment

The relationship between Spiritual Leadership and Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment is based on social learning theory (Bandura, 1977) which shows that people observe, learn and imitate the behavior and actions of their role models, indicating that leaders can model behavior to their followers. Based on social learning theory, Anser et al. (2020) argue that employees learn and practice the spiritual leader's vision, altruistic values, and hopes/beliefs, as well as showing positive social emotions, such as forgiveness, gratitude, and helping others which gives them the spiritual enthusiasm to make extra efforts volunteer in preserving the natural environment, because preserving nature and the environment is a moral issue (Khan et al., 2019). Spiritual leadership is interested in developing individuals' ecological values (Afsar et al., 2015) that trigger their engagement in wise environmentally friendly behavior (Anser et al., 2020). Research by Anser et al. (2020) and Ali et al. (2020) shows that Spiritual Leadership has a significant positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment. Kaya's research (2015) although it does not specifically discuss environmental care behavior, his research shows that Spiritual Leadership has a significant positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

H1: Spiritual Leadership has a significant positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment among employees at Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital.

E. The Influence of Spiritual Leadership on Self-Efficacy

A leader with a Spiritual Leadership style tends to allow his followers to pursue greater life goals, meaningful work, transcendence, altruism, and a sense of togetherness (Fry, 2003). This process has the potential to provide a greater feeling of harmony between organizational spirituality and personal spirituality as well as an increased sense of meaning, self-transcendence, and connectedness (Afsar et al., 2015) thereby generating confidence in followers that they can face and resolve a problem and prepare yourself in the challenges of the future. Research by Chen et al. (2011) shows that Spiritual Leadership has a positive effect on followers' spiritual attributes toward the inner self (self-esteem and self-efficacy).

H2: Spiritual Leadership has a significant positive effect on Self-efficacy among employees at Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital.

F. The Influence of Self-Efficacy on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment

Self-efficacy refers to the belief that one has the power to produce desired outcomes (Bandura et al., 1997). Derived from Bandura's (1977) socio-cognitive theory, which explains that when individuals consider themselves capable of performing a task, they prepare themselves for the risks and uncertainties associated with the task (Somech & Drach-Zahavy, 2000). Schutte and Bhullar (2017) argue that negative environmental changes and related behaviors trigger motivation, self-efficacy and self-responsibility, encouraging the person to engage in activities that can undo the negative event. Regarding environmental awareness actions, factors such as easy and fast information, role models and pro-environmental actions in the past give rise to confidence that they will be able to carry out similar actions and face challenges related to the environment in the future (Lauren et al, 2016). In this context, employees utilize this for pro-environmental behavior, for example OCBE (Jugert et al., 2016). Ullah et al.'s research. (2021) shows that Self Efficacy has a positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment. Meanwhile, other research, although it does not specifically discuss pro-environmental behavior, shows that Self Efficacy has a positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) (Choong et al., 2019; Erum et al., 2020).

H3: Self Efficacy has a significant positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment among employees at Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital

G. The Influence of Self Efficacy in Mediating the Influence of Spiritual Leadership on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment

Boiral et al. (2015) found that the higher a company's managers' perception of being able to take environmental action, the more likely they are to adopt proactive behavior regarding environmental issues. Workers with higher levels of self-efficacy tend to carry out proactive behavior in the environment (Jex et al., 2001; Walumbwa et al., 2011; Nielsen et al. in Testa et al., 2018).

H4: Self Efficacy mediates the positive influence of Spiritual Leadership on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment in employees at Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This research is associative research with a quantitative approach. This research was conducted at the Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital. The population in this study was all employees at Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital, totaling 205 people. The sample is a portion or representative of the population to be studied (Arikunto, 2010). The sampling technique in this research uses a simple random sampling probability sampling technique, namely a sampling technique that provides an equal opportunity for each element (member) of the population to be randomly selected as a sample member, without paying attention to strata in the population (Sugiyono, 2014). This technique is used with the assumption that OCBE for Harapan Keluarga Hospital employees can be carried out by anyone regardless of their

strata. Using a Likert scale of 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), data was gathered using a questionnaire. Sixty-four assertions that are statement items make up the questionnaire's items. The study data was then examined utilizing clever PLS 3.0 software and the Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM).

IV. RESULTS

Table 1. Panel Data Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Relationship Between Variabel	Coefficient	T Statistics	P Values
<i>Spiritual Leadership ->OCBE</i>	0,258	2,183	0,030
<i>Spiritual Leadership ->Self-efficacy</i>	0,667	13,723	0,000
<i>Self-efficacy ->OCBE</i>	0,212	2,210	0,028
<i>Spiritual Leadership ->Self-efficacy ->OCBE</i>	0,141	2,083	0,038

Sources: Research Data, 2023

Based on the table above, the relationship between variables Table 1 above provides an explanation of the relationship between the variables (results of the hypothesis test):

- Spiritual leadership significantly improves OCBE, with a coefficient of 0.258, t-statistic of 2.183 > 1.96 and P-value of 0.030 < 0.05. The first hypothesis (H1) is therefore accepted. In other words, the better the Spiritual Leadership's effectiveness, the higher the OCBE will be for the Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital staff.
- Self-efficacy is positively and significantly impacted by spiritual leadership, as shown by the coefficient value of 0.667, t statistic value of 13.723 > 1.96, and P value of 0.000 < 0.05. Therefore, the second hypothesis (H2) is confirmed. Accordingly, the personnel at Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital have higher levels of self-efficacy the more successful Spiritual Leadership is.
- Self-efficacy significantly improves OCBE, as evidenced by its coefficient value of 0.212, the t-statistic value of 2.210 > 1.96, and P value of 0.028 < 0.05. The fourth hypothesis (H4) is therefore accepted. Therefore, the OCBE of the staff at Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital will increase in proportion to their self-efficacy.
- The role of Self-efficacy can mediate the positive influence of Spiritual Leadership on OCBE with a coefficient value of 0.141, a t-statistic value of 2.083 > 1.96, and a P-value of 0.038 < 0.05. So, the sixth hypothesis (H6) is accepted. This means that the influence of Spiritual Leadership on OCBE in Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital employees can be through Self-efficacy. The Self-efficacy variable is included in the perfect variable category because the influence of Spiritual Leadership on OCBE directly decreases to zero when the Self-efficacy variable is included.

V. DISCUSSION

A. The Influence of Spiritual Leadership on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment

The results of this research show that Spiritual Leadership has a significant positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment so the first hypothesis (H1) is accepted. This means that the more effective the Spiritual Leadership, the higher the OCBE of the employees at Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital. Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (OCBE) is employee discretionary behavior in supporting environmentally related practices and initiatives within the organization even though it is not formally appreciated by the organization (Boiral, 2009; Daily et al., 2009; Robertson & Barling, 2017; Ullah et al. al., 2021). On the other hand, Spiritual Leadership refers to a leadership approach that focuses on spiritual values, ethics, altruistic love, and higher goals in guiding and motivating organizational members (Fry, 2003; Afsar et al., 2015). This leadership style is able to trigger the development of a deeper awareness of social and environmental responsibility. Employees who are led by Spiritual Leadership principles tend to have a higher awareness and commitment to environmental protection efforts and environmentally friendly practices. Values such as empathy, compassion, and social responsibility espoused by Spiritual Leadership can encourage active employee participation in OCBE, such as supporting recycling programs, reducing resource use, and contributing to the organization's sustainability efforts. Thus, the concept of Spiritual Leadership functions as a driver of intrinsic motivation for employees to take the initiative in supporting a sustainable work environment at Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital

Based on Bandura's (1977) social learning theory, the significant positive influence of Spiritual Leadership on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (OCBE) among employees at Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital can be seen as the result of the interaction between the organizational environment and individual behavior. This theory emphasizes how individuals learn from the social environment and role models around them. In this context, Spiritual Leadership functions as a strong role model in shaping norms and values related to the workplace environment. Spiritual Leadership, with its emphasis on ethics, empathy, altruistic love, and social responsibility, provides a model of behavior that employees live by. Employees who are exposed to this kind of leadership style can internalize these values through a social learning process. They can see how their leaders demonstrate concern and commitment to environmental issues and then adapt these behaviors in OCBE. For example, through observations and interactions with leaders who highlight environmentally friendly practices, employees are likely to understand that participation in OCBE is an integral part of the organizational culture that is valued and cared for. This is reinforced by the respondents' answers to the questionnaire which gave a very high average result for each indicator of the Spiritual Leadership variable because the respondents really believed in the great vision of their leader, they pinned their hopes and

confidence in the success of the organization on their leader and modeled the altruistic love behavior that they saw. look at their leaders, one of whom is OCBE. The results of this research are in line with and support the results of previous research by Kaya (2015), Ali et al. (2020), and Anser et al. (2020) that Spiritual Leadership directly has a significant positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment.

B. The Influence of Spiritual Leadership on Self-efficacy

The results of this research show that Spiritual Leadership has a significant positive effect on Self-efficacy, so the second hypothesis (H2) is accepted. This means that the more effective Spiritual Leadership is, the higher the Self-efficacy of the employees at Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital. Spiritual Leadership refers to a leadership approach that integrates spiritual values, an ethic of altruistic love and a higher purpose in inspiring and guiding organizational members (Fry, 2003). Self-efficacy, on the other hand, refers to an individual's belief in his or her own ability to successfully execute tasks and achieve desired goals (Bandura, 1997). In the context of Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital, the positive and significant influence of Spiritual Leadership on Self-efficacy indicates that the spiritual leadership style is able to have a strong impact on employee self-confidence. Spiritual Leadership functions as a behavioral model that radiates positive and inspiring values to employees (Anser et al., 2020). Leaders who practice spirituality as the basis of leadership tend to set examples of work ethics, responsibility and integrity as well as altruistic love. This can influence employees' views of themselves and their own abilities. The practice of spiritual values in daily life by leaders can help employees internalize the belief that they are also able to face existing tasks and challenges (Chen et al., 2011). In addition, positive communication and interaction with leaders who uphold spiritual values can strengthen employees' self-concept (Anser et al., 2020). Recognition of their contribution to a larger, sustainable goal can increase their sense of competence and self-confidence. When employees feel valued and supported by leaders, they tend to feel more able to overcome challenges and achieve goals (Eliot, 2020). The importance of identification and self-empowerment factors in Spiritual Leadership also plays an important role. Employees who feel they have an important role in realizing the values and goals of a larger organization can feel more empowered and confident in taking action steps that contribute to achieving those goals (Afsar et al., 2015; Chen et al., 2021). This contributes to the development of higher Self-efficacy.

Based on Bandura's (1977) social learning theory, the significant positive influence of Spiritual Leadership on Self-efficacy among employees at Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital can be seen through learning mechanisms and social interaction. This theory emphasizes that individuals learn through observation and interaction with the environment and role models around them. In this context, Spiritual Leadership functions as a role model that teaches spiritual values, ethics, altruistic love and social responsibility, which in turn can shape employee self-confidence or self-efficacy. Spiritual Leadership creates an environment where

employees are exposed to positive values related to responsibility, empathy, and empowerment (Anser et al., 2020). Employees who have leaders who live out these values tend to internalize these views. With direct experience or through observation, they learn that environmental responsibility and awareness of the impact of their actions are important. This can help build confidence that they have the ability to make positive changes in matters related to the environment that occur at Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital. The results of this study support research conducted by Chen et al. (2011) that Spiritual Leadership has a positive effect on followers' spiritual attributes toward inner self (self esteem & self efficacy) as well as research by Chen et al. (2022) that Spiritual Leadership has a positive effect on goal self-concordance and self-efficacy.

C. The Influence of Self Efficacy on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment

The research results show that self-efficacy has a significant positive effect on OCBE, so the fourth hypothesis (H4) is accepted. This means that the higher the Self-efficacy, the higher the OCBE of the employees at Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital. This shows the important role of self-confidence in encouraging active participation in environmentally supportive behavior within the organization. Self-efficacy as an individual's belief in his or her ability to overcome tasks and challenges (Bandura, 1997) acts as a strong internal motivator for employees to behave positively towards environmentally friendly practices.

In the framework of Bandura's Social Cognitive theory (1997), self-efficacy is considered a key factor that influences individual behavior. High self-confidence in one's own ability to overcome obstacles and achieve goals encourages individuals to take the initiative in carrying out positive actions. In the context of Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital, high self-efficacy encourages employees to be more actively involved in OCBE, such as participation in recycling programs or reducing resource use. The interaction between Self-efficacy and OCBE can be explained through the concept of reinforcement in the past. Employees who have experienced success in OCBE behaviors, such as participating in environmental activities or conveying ideas for sustainable practices in the past, will have the confidence to repeat similar behaviors. Success in one of these behaviors can strengthen their self-confidence in their ability to influence the work environment through other positive actions (Bandura, 1997). In addition, self-efficacy can also influence individuals' perceptions of the impact and relevance of their actions on the environment. High self-confidence can make employees more likely to see themselves as effective agents of change (Cherian & Jacob, 2013) which then encourages participation in OCBE as a means of making meaningful contributions. The results of this study support previous research conducted by Choong et al. (2019), Erum et al. (2020) and Ullah et al. (2021) which shows that Self-efficacy has a positive effect on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment.

D. The Influence of Self-Efficacy in Mediating the Influence of Spiritual Leadership on Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment

The results of this research show that the role of Self-efficacy can mediate the positive influence of Spiritual Leadership on OCBE, so that the sixth hypothesis (H6) is accepted. This means that the influence of Spiritual Leadership on OCBE in Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital employees can be through Self-efficacy. Spiritual Leadership with an emphasis on ethics, social responsibility, altruistic love and concern for higher goals, can provide guidance and inspiration for employees to behave in a supportive environment thereby giving rise to self-efficacy in employees that they can do the same (Anser et al., 2020). An individual's self-confidence in their ability to succeed in positive actions that influence the environment can be a factor that facilitates or limits the implementation of these values in real action. In this case, Self-efficacy functions as a link between Spiritual Leadership and OCBE. Employees who are inspired by the spiritual values embodied by their leaders will internalize these values in their own belief that they have the capability to act in accordance with these values as referred to by Bandura (1997) as one way of developing Self-efficacy in a person. They believe that their actions can have a positive impact on the environment, and this belief can motivate them to participate in behaviors that support the environment. It is important to recognize that this mediation process can also be influenced by other factors, such as organizational culture, work environment, and individual motivation. However, the role of Self-efficacy as a link between Spiritual Leadership and OCBE provides a deeper understanding of how individuals' beliefs in their abilities play an important role in bridging the values embodied by leaders and positive behavior that supports the environment.

The results of this research indicate that Spiritual Leadership as a leadership style in relation to OCBE can be mediated by self-efficacy, thereby supporting and adding to the results of previous research by Ullah et al. (2021) who researched the influence of Responsible Leadership, Inclusive Leadership, Authentic Leadership and Supportive Leadership in relation to OCBE through Self-efficacy. The results of this research also support several previous studies which, although not specifically discussing Spiritual Leadership or OCBE, enrich the results of their research on the influence of various leadership styles on employee discretionary behavior (OCB) through Self-efficacy, such as research by Adewale & Ghavifekr (2019); Almahdali et al. (2021); Pratiwi & Nawangsari (2021).

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Organizational Citizenship Behavior for the Environment (OCBE), and self-efficacy of workers at Harapan Keluarga Mataram Hospital are all positively and significantly impacted by spiritual leadership. The association between Spiritual Leadership and OCBE is also mediated by Self-efficacy. This research provides valuable insight into the importance of Spiritual Leadership in improving OCBE and related factors at Harapan Keluarga

Mataram Hospital, which can serve as a guide for management and leadership development in similar institutions.

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